

Sentimental Analysis of Users Review on Usage Experience

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Abstract— Sentiment Analysis is a computational study to extract subjective information from the text. Nowadays, digital reviews play a vital role in enhancing global communications among users and persuading new users in finding out if the site is actually worth-it. Provide a platform for consumers to share their experiences and deliver real insights about the site as if it is trust-worthy. In order to extract valuable insights of the reviews from the users, into positive and negative sentiment and showing the relative percentage of likeness the Vader sentiment module and the nltk package with Django is used.

Keywords—Vader, Unsupervised Learning Algorithm, Django.

I. INTRODUCTION

Reviews or feedback of a site throw out more information about the site as how the user experience is, is the site worth-it for what it is been used for, etc. In this study, we use the Vader sentiment module from the nltk package of Django to classify the sentiment of the user as positive or negative. Process flows like this, as the feedback is entered it is evaluated and only the contents with sentiment are crawled out avoiding the rest of the unwanted words. Lastly, the overall sentiment in the feedback content is shown to the user in a percentage form showing that for how much extent to they liked the site also the result is outputted as voice for better convenience. In addition it also providing information for job seekers as if it's worth it to use this site for their intention.

II. RELATED WORKS

Antony et. al.[1] this study shows a customer feedback review on a product utilizing opinion mining, text mining, and sentiments, which have been affected by changing their opinion on a specific product. This delivers you with a sentimental analysis of numerous smartphone opinions separating them into Positive, Negative, and Neutral Behaviour.

Esha et. al.[2] this paper deliberates how to apply a Support Vector Machine (SVM) machine learning algorithm to classify sentiments for product reviews that analyses different datasets to measure the polarity of reviews whether positive or negative and resulting models are tested to measure the accuracy of SVM algorithm.

Lin et. al.[3] this paper is based on some features, a number of comparative tests using classification algorithms, feature representations, and review length have been conducted. We performed a statistical analysis after crawling an enormous amount of real data and discovered that mobile application reviews share the following four traits: Power-law

distribution, short average length, a wide range of lengths, and a substantial polarity difference.

Anant et. al.[4] this paper has covered many standardization techniques for NLP, including their significance and implementation in Python using the NLTK package. A comparison of Logistic Regression and Naive Bayes models is also discussed and implemented. Resulting in the Logistic Regression being more accurate than Naive Bayes.

Kushal et. al.[5] this study is a fresh method for a dynamic feature-based summary of consumer reviews that are relevant to the product's field. Results show that the suggested approaches accomplish their tasks very effectively and efficiently. The relevant passages relating to each feature-opinions combination are extracted from the reviews and placed in the corresponding feature-based cluster to construct feature-based precise reviews.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study enhances a method to analyze online reviews from users as reviews are a great source to get to know more about a site and its usage.

The analysis is carried out in six stages mainly,

In the first stage, the data that is entered by the user as feedback which is the review data is crawled through as a part of analyzing data for further procedures that are to be done.

Next in the second step, the entered data is converted into small letters to eliminate the conflict of validating through both upper and lower case letters.

In the third step, the resulting raw data obtained from the user which has been lowercased is gone through a pre-processing stage where deletion of inaccurate data is done.

In the fourth step, the words other than sentiment keywords ie; stopwords are removed by using the stopword attribute of the nltk package which helps to identify the stopword present in the feedback entered and to remove it from the data.

In the fifth step, The digits and special symbols are eliminated by using the isdigit() function provided by python. Also, the special character is removed by using the regex form provided by the python language.

Finally, in the sixth step, the aspect score is calculated. This is done by using the polarity_scores, a module within the SentimentIntensityAnalyzer package of the Vader tool. The polarity scores are evaluated and the resulting value is

passed through an equation that outputs the final value which is in the form of a percentage value showing to how extent the user liked the site and its functionalities.

This is the whole procedure that is done to evaluate the sentiment included in the feedback that the user enters and show the percentage of likelihood of a site and its user experience

```
from vaderSentiment.vaderSentiment import SentimentIntensityAnalyzer
import nltk
import re
from nltk.corpus import stopwords
# from django.shortcuts import render_to_response
# Create your views here.
nltk.download('stopwords')
set(stopwords.words('english'))

def my_form(request):
    return render(request, 'form.html')
```

```
def my_post(request):
    if request.method == "POST":
        stop_words = stopwords.words('english')
        # my contribution
        stop_words.remove('very')
        stop_words.remove('not')

        #convert to lowercase
        text1 = request.POST['text1'].lower()

        # my contribution
        text_final = ''.join(i for i in text1 if not i.isdigit())
        net_ext=re.sub('[^a-zA-Z0-9\n]', '', text_final)

        #remove stopwords
        processed_doc1 = ' '.join((i for i in net_ext.split() if i not in stop_words))

        sa = SentimentIntensityAnalyzer()
        dd = sa.polarity_scores(text+processed_doc1)
        compound = round((1 + dd['compound'])/2, 2)
        final=compound*100

        return render(request, 'form.html',{'final': final, 'text1':net_ext,
            'text2':dd['pos'], 'text5':dd['neg'], 'text4':compound, 'text3':dd['neu']})
    else:
        return redirect('my_form')
```

IV. RESULTS

The study throws –out the result of for how much of extent (represented in percentage) the user liked the site and its provided functionalities. This is achieved by calculating the polarity scores of the positivity or negativity content present in the feedback provided by the user.

V. CONCLUSION

Nowadays we depend on online reviews to select trustworthy sites to search on. Online reviews have developed a platform for building trust and others. We attain this by showing sentiment analysis of pre-users reviews and classifying the reviews into positive and negative sentiment by using the Vader tool and nltk package. Crawling through the text removes all not-sentiment words and also removes all digits and special symbols and thereby calculating polarity scores and outputting the overall percentage of the likeness of the site. This planned extension of work will be very helpful and will enhance user satisfaction and trust.

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